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Occupational Stress and Performance of Non-Academic Staff of Tertiary
Institutions in Lagos-State, Nigeria.

Akeke, Adenike Rita¹ & Ismaila, Yusuf Olajide²

^{1,2}Department Business Education

College of Vocational and Entrepreneurship Education
Lagos State University of Education, Oto/Ijanikin, Lagos.
ninikx2002@yahoo.com

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Abstract

This study established the effect of occupational stress on performance of non-academic staff of tertiary institutions in Lagos State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study examined the effect of role ambiguity, role conflict and the poor working conditions on non-academic staff of tertiary institutions in Lagos State. The study adopted a descriptive survey design and the population covered all 228 non-academic employees of Federal Technical College of Education, Akoka, Yaba College of Technology, Yaba, and Lagos State University of Education, Ijanikin. The sample size was 145 which were determined using Yamane sampling model. Descriptively, frequency and percentage were used to analyze the bio data of the respondents while regression analysis was used to analyse data collected. The estimation techniques are R-square, F-statistics and P-value. The results of the analysis discovered that role ambiguity, role conflict and poor working conditions have positive and significant effect on performance of non-academic staff of tertiary institutions in Lagos State. In relation to the findings of this study, it was concluded that occupational stress has a significant impact on how well employees execute their jobs. It is, therefore, recommended that the role of non-academic staff of tertiary institutions must be cleared to them, content must be explicit to guide against stress and conflict in the workplace. Institutions should also implement management programmes aimed at controlling and minimizing the level of stress that employees experience.

Keywords: Occupational stress, employee performance, role ambiguity, role conflict, poor working conditions

Introduction

Occupational stress has been a big problem for workers and employers alike due to its impact on performance. Stress has become a global issue and a serious worry for employees in all workplaces (Brony, 2018). Many people are experiencing occupational stress as a result of working under pressure, working longer hours, and other job-related demands (Chandan, 2012).

Workers tend to feel stressed when they are overcrowded, have to maintain positive interactions with colleagues, lower-ranking employees and other supervisors, have too much work overload,

different activities created as a result of inter-role conflicts, unattainable deadlines, a lack of promotion opportunities, a lack of certainty in roles creativity, and work long hours. Senior management's job rotation of employees can also contribute to workplace stress.

Most institutions accomplish performance by overloading people with work in order to meet deadlines, which has mental and physical consequences for the employees and occasionally resulting in something opposed to what these organisations intend to achieve (Kashim, 2021). Nonetheless, role demand can be unpleasant when it is high (role overload) (Johnson et al. 2005), as it increases employees' responsibility. Several studies have found that occupational stress is linked to low fulfillment, absences from work, and low engagement, all of which are likely to affect worker efficiency and productivity (Chang & Lu, 2007).

These days' organisations pay greater attention to their employees than in the past; the implications of the trauma their workforce have experienced cannot be overstated because they continue to make enormous demands on them to achieve. Although many researches have been conducted on the association between occupational stress and performance, the results have been inconsistent; some are notably beneficial, while others are detrimental. Furthermore, previous research investigations have been conducted in a variety of settings, including banks (Banyi, Ndah & Wuchu 2021, Amoako, Gyamfi & David 2017; Annah, Mary & Kilungu 2021), oil palm plantations (Asamoah-Appiah & Aggrey-Fynn, 2019), judiciary (Mbinya & Mose 2022), and institutions of the public sector (Kitole, Idua & Matata, 2019), but little research have been accomplished in the field of education. It is incorrect to believe that prior studies in different contexts will produce homogeneous results in the education sector. The education industry helps to develop leaders who lead with emotion and authentic values. In this regard, the academic industry serves as the cornerstone for social and economic advancement by providing significant perspectives on life. Furthermore, the higher education sector penetrates all elements of nation formation as a critical factor in workforce growth and a byproduct of societal culture.

Given the economic importance of the educational sector, having a comprehension of how occupational stress affects worker performance is critical. As a result, this type of research will undoubtedly contribute to the literature. This study aims to investigate the effects of occupational stress on the performance of non-academic staff in tertiary institutions.

Literature Review

Stress can be viewed as a condition that works against all employees at work. The prevalence of stress in job settings is a cause for worry due to its significant impact on workplace costs and worker functioning. From the point of view of psychology, stress is frequently defined as an unfavourable person-environment relationship (Lazarus, 2019), which is associated with poor psychological and physical health. This concept contains the idea that stress should be viewed as a multifaceted phenomenon that might include how people perceive and react to events and the environment. Stress is commonly regarded as a mental condition, but it can also have an impact on physical health and performance. According to Aydin (2018), occupational stress is viewed as psychological and physical pressure that emerges in an individual due to a mismatch of job

demands and available resources. Occupational stress is described as the sense of disconnect between environmental expectations (stressors) and individual capacity to meet these needs (Topper, 2017; Vermut & Steensma, 2015; Ornels & Kleiner, 2013). Undie, Ukpata, & Iyortsuun (2018), for example, suggested that the reasons of occupational stress include potential loss of employment and security, extended periods of sitting or prolonged lifting, a lack of safety, complexities of a recurrent, and a lack of independence in the workplace.

Furthermore, occupational stress could be caused by an inadequate supply of resources and equipment; hours of work (such as working extra hours or excessively); and organisational conditions are all factors that contribute to employee stress. Occupational stress frequently results in employee discontent, job mobility, burnout, poor work performance, and less effective interpersonal interactions at work (Khadid & Amber, 2018). Trina (2018), claimed that treatments such as recognizing or determining the indicators of stress, determining the likely reasons of the indications, and proposing potential remedies for each sign are necessary.

In line with Annah, Mary, and Kilungu (2019), stress is an unpredictable condition that occurs when an individual comes across with an opportunity, limitation, or demand connected to what he wishes, with the result seen to be both unclear and crucial. According to this definition, stress is not just unpleasant, but it can also be beneficial when it provides opportunities for growth. Annah, Mary, and Kilungu, (2019), defined stress as a person's adaptive response to a stimulus that imposes both mental and physical demands on them. Furthermore, Mohammed (2019) defines stress as an unpleasant psychological experience associated with predictable biochemical, emotional, cognitive, and behavioural adjustments aimed at either changing the events or coping with their consequences. Alasa and Amuen (2020) highlighted role ambiguity, role conflict, and bad working conditions as primary elements of occupational stress.

Role Ambiguity

Role ambiguity is characterised as the absence of precision in comprehending the actions required to achieve stated personal objectives (Alasa & Amuen 2020). Role ambiguity is a concept used to express the lack of understanding, absolute certainty, and predictability that one could expect in terms of job behaviour. Role ambiguity happens when employees do not believe they have the required knowledge to fulfill their role effectively and are unsure of their expectations (Kashim, 2021). In Robbins and Judge (2020), role ambiguity refers to unclear employees' behaviours. Likewise, it is referring to as an emotional situation in which employees may experience work stress and ultimately affects turnover rates and job satisfaction level (Azzahra, Ilmi, & Wijaya, 2021). Numerous researches have examined the repercussions of role ambiguity, both at the individual and team levels, and have found that effort is reduced. The presence of ambiguity in objectives influences employees' knowledge of what they are expected to do, raise concerns about how they will accomplish their own performance objectives, and creates uncertainty about how their performance will be evaluated and the implications of completing or not accomplishing their objectives (Rogalsky, 2016).

Nevertheless, if an individual is unable to complete a given duty, it often causes tension in the workplace. Thus, if an employee is unsure of the job demands or strategies to achieve, he or she may feel task ambiguity, resulting in a loss in job satisfaction.

Role Conflict

Role conflict occurs when members of an organisation disagree on the subject matter of a task undertaken by one or more of them. Role conflict is associated with boundaries of role between organisational members, which can be especially intense in multiple leadership systems because task conflict amongst multiple leaders, as well as among themselves and other members of the organisation, can result in role stress. Role stress is often classified into two types: conflict and ambiguity. Role conflict emerges when workers are presented with contradictory or conflicting expectations (Banyi, Ndah, & Wochu, 2021), because of its negative repercussions, such as discontent, anxiety, decreased commitment, and lower performance.

Poor Working conditions

This refers to the physical conditions of the workplace, encompassing high levels of noise, high or low illumination, heat, not enough ventilation systems, and all of the stimuli that assault a worker's senses and may impact his moods and general mental state. Also, the physical design of the office is in bad operating order. If an office is poorly planned and overcrowded with individuals who demand frequent touch, it produces inadequate communication networks and leads to poor working relationships, which can cause employee stress.

Employee Performance

Job performance can be said to be the behaviour an individual displays as a member of the institution to fulfill the expectation, requirement or formalised role needs of the institution. This also applies to the value, quality, or amount of work employees performed by an employee. Employee productivity has an impact on and improves the institution's overall performance. Job performance refers to the results that employees achieved via their work throughout a given time period. According to Anu and Kumar (2018), job performance can be defined as the accomplishment of a specific activity, with success measured against pre-established standards of accuracy, completeness, economy, and speed. It is also defined as "an activity in which a person successfully completes the task/goal specified for him, subject to the normal constraint of making reasonable use of available resources."

Performance refers to an individual's effective completion of responsibilities assigned by an organisation in accordance with specified criteria, as well as the efficient utilisation of resources in an ever-changing setting (Qadoos, 2015). Every institution has been formed with specific goals to attain. These objectives can be met by utilising resources such as persons, machinery, materials, and money. Performance is an important, but not the sole, criterion for future career advancement and labour market success. Although there may be exceptions, high performers advance more quickly within an organisation and have more career prospects than low performers. As a result,

employees must consider performance to be extremely important. (Vanscotter, Motowidlo, & Cross, 2010; Sabine & Michael, 2001).

Theoretical Review

Sociological theories, particularly the approach of industrial sociologists, have highlighted the social organisation of work as the fundamental cause of occupational injury, disease, and stress. According to industrial sociologists, the root causes of occupational wellness and stress are power structures, institutionalised conflicts of interest between worker security and efficiency, and the social division of labour, the process of labour, industrial relations, and politics (McIntyre, 1998; Peterson, 1994).

Substantial legislative reforms in occupational health and safety and workers' compensation have transformed how people think of workplace health from an individual and marginalised process to one with significant economic and political ramifications (Kenny, 1994a; 1994b; Willis, 1989). These modifications have resulted in a revised understanding of occupational sickness as a social process with features that are not individualised, unique, or distinctive. Furthermore, sociologists contend that every occupational illness or injury has physiological and ergonomic elements whose effects are controlled by social conditions, especially work organisation and the sociology of medical knowledge related to the illness or injury (Figlio, 1982). Prior to being designated as a syndrome, occupational illnesses are negotiated for their social and political meaning, as well as their numerous economic and social ramifications (Willis, 1994).

The paradox of this process is that, despite growing acknowledgment that these kinds of conditions are public issues, personal remedies are being sought. With a few major exemptions (Levi, 1998), this has proven true for occupational stress. The most significant contribution of sociological approaches to occupational sickness is that "occupational health and safety is now increasingly an industrial relations issue between capital and labour; it is now beginning to mediate the social relations of production" (Willis, 1994). Consequently, the emphasis has switched from a pessimistic acknowledgment that there will be fatalities in the work process to a legally mandated duty that companies offer a safe workplace for all employees. The cost of compensation is progressively influencing occupational health and safety practices and procedures, and thereby labour processes themselves (McIntyre, 1998).

A number of past researchers had provided empirical support statement about the relationship that exists between occupational stress and employees' performance for instance, in the study of Mufeed (2023) the result showed that both work overload and inadequate compensation have significant negative impact on employees' performance. In this vein, study of Muhammad (2019) found that there is significant relationship between work stress and employee productivity. Livinus, Okpara and Victor (2020) showed that the null hypotheses were rejected and the alternative hypotheses accepted, thereby concluded that significant relationship exists between stress and employee performance. The study of Alasa and Amuen (2020) revealed that work demand, role conflict and role ambiguity negatively and significantly influence employees' job

performance. Furthermore, Kashim's (2021) study indicated that work stress can affect employee performance when stress is not handled well, absenteeism, turnover, and medical compensation increase and productivity decreases. Lastly, Akintoye (2022) found that job safety, workload, and salary and rewards which served as proxies for job stress all have significant effect on job stress.

Methodology

A descriptive research design was used for the study. The population of the study covers all public tertiary institutions in Lagos State. A convenient sampling method was used to select three institutions which comprises of Federal Technical College, Akoka., Yaba College of Technology, Yaba, and Lagos State University of Education, Ijanikin with a population of 228 non-academic staff. Yammane (1967) sample size model was used to determine 145 participants. Questionnaire was administered among the sampled participants and was carried out for a period of 3 months. The independent variable was proxied by poor working conditions, role ambiguity and role conflict as measured by Alasa and Amuen (2020), Kashim (2021), and Akintoye (2022) while dependent variable measures were adapted from Anu and Kumar (2018). Data collected was coded, classified and tabulated. The data was analysed using descriptive statistics, while inferential statistics such as multiple regression analysis was used to analyse the data collected.

Results and Discussion

Role Ambiguity and Employees' Performance

The analysis of the respondents' scores on two variables of role ambiguity and tertiary institutions workers performance in Lagos-State were computed and subjected to simple regression analysis. From Table 1, the R (correlation Coefficient) gives a positive value of 0.762; this indicates that there is a very strong and positive relationship between role ambiguity and employees performance of tertiary institutions. The R^2 is a portion of the total variation in the dependent variable that is explained by the variation in the independent variables. From the results obtained, R^2 is equal to 0.581, this implies that role ambiguity brought about 58.1% variance in tertiary institutions workers performance in Lagos-State, this is further proven by the adjusted R^2 that shows the goodness of fit of the model which gives a value of 0.577, implying that when all errors are corrected and adjustments are made, the model can only account for 57.7% by role ambiguity; while the remaining 42.3% are explained by the error term in the model as shown in Table 1.

The unstandardized beta co-efficient of role ambiguity is 517 with $t = 13.568$ and $(p = 0.000 < 0.05)$. These results showed that role ambiguity has a positive relationship with employee's performance of tertiary institution. This suggests that work is not complicated as it does not require sophisticated skills; duties assigned to us are well defined and clear to us.

From the Table 1 discussion, and by F-Stat. 184.080 p -value $.000 < .05$, it showed that the null hypothesis, role ambiguity does not significantly affect employees performance of tertiary institutions and is not true therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. Based on this, we accepted the alternative hypothesis that role ambiguity has effect on employees' performance of tertiary institutions.

Table 1: Role Ambiguity and Employees’ Performance

Variable	Co-eff.	Std. Error	t-value	Sig.
Constant	2.048	0.142	14.438	0.000
Role Ambiguity	0.517	0.038	13.568	0.000
R	0.762			
R Square	0.581			
Adj. R Square	0.577			
F Stat.	184.080(.000)			

Dependent variable: Employees’ Performance

Role Conflict and Employees’ Performance

The analysis of the respondents’ scores on two variables of role conflict and tertiary institutions employee’s performance were computed and subjected to simple regression analysis. From Table 2, the R (correlation Coefficient) gives a positive value of 0.890; this indicates that there is a strong and positive relationship between role conflict and on performance employees of tertiary institutions. The R² is a portion of the total variation in the dependent variable that is explained by the variation in the independent variables. From the results obtained, R² is equal to 0.791, this implies that role conflict brought about 79.1% variance on employees performance of tertiary institutions, this is further proven by the adjusted R² that shows the goodness of fit of the model which gives a value of 0.790, implying that when all errors are corrected and adjustments are made, the model can only account for 79% by role conflict; while the remaining 21% are explained by the error term in the model as shown in Table 2.

The unstandardized beta co-efficient of role conflict is 0.789 with t= 22.464 and (p= 0.000 < 0.05). These results showed that role conflict has a positive relationship on employees’ performance of tertiary institutions. This implies that schemes of work are well defined and well supervised during working hours and members of Staff who are exposed to aggression in the workplace are more likely to have unnecessary arguments with employee.

From the Table 2 discussion, and by F-Stat. 504.624 p-value .000 < .05, it showed that the null hypothesis, role conflict does not significantly affect employees performance of tertiary institutions and is not true therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. Based on this, we accepted the alternative hypothesis that role conflict has effect on employees’ performance of tertiary institutions.

Table 2: Role Conflict and Employees’ Performance

Variable	Co-eff.	Std. Error	t-value	Sig.
Constant	0.897	0.137	6.570	0.000
Role Conflict	0.789	0.035	22.464	0.000
R	0.890			
R Square	0.791			
Adj. R Square	0.790			
F Stat.	504.624(0.000)			

Dependent variable: Employees' Performance

Poor working condition and employee's performance

The analysis of the respondents' scores on two variables of poor working condition and employees' performance of tertiary institutions were computed and subjected to simple regression analysis. From Table 3 the R (correlation Coefficient) gives a positive value of 0.948; this indicates that there is strong and positive relationship between poor working condition and employees' performance of tertiary institutions. The R² is a portion of the total variation in the dependent variable that is explained by the variation in the independent variables. From the results obtained, R² is equal to 0.900, this implies that poor working condition brought about 90% variance on employees performance of tertiary institutions, this is further proven by the adjusted R² that shows the goodness of fit of the model which gives a value of 0.899, implying that when all errors are corrected and adjustments are made, the model can only account for 89.9% by employees performance of tertiary institutions; while the remaining 10.1% are explained by the error term in the model as shown in Table 3.

The unstandardized beta co-efficient of poor working condition is 0.794 with t= 34.523 and (p= 0.000 < 0.05). These results showed that poor working condition has a positive relationship with employees performance of tertiary institutions. This implies that lack of social support from colleagues and poor interpersonal relations causes increase in poor working condition and tasks allocated to us are done even in poor working conditions with all my capability and expectations. From the Table 3 discussion, and by F-Stat. 1191.852 p-value .000 < .05, it showed that the null hypothesis, poor working condition does not significantly affect employees performance of tertiary institutions is not true therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. Based on this, we accepted the alternative hypothesis that poor working condition have effect on employee performance of tertiary institutions.

Table 3: Poor Working Conditions and Employees' Performance

Variable	Co-eff.	Std. Error	t-value	Sig.
Constant	0.849	0.090	9.397	0.000
Poor working condition	0.794	0.023	34.523	0.000
R	0.948			
R Square	0.900			
Adj. R Square	0.899			
F Stat.	1191.852(.000)			

Dependent variable: Employees' Performance

Conclusion

The study seeks to examine the effect of occupational stress on performance of non-academic staff of tertiary institutions. Rarely has any study of this nature been carried out in the educational sector in the developing countries particularly in Nigeria.

The findings indicate that role ambiguity has positive significant effect on employees' performance of tertiary institutions. In addition, the result revealed that role conflict is significantly related to employees' performance of tertiary institutions. Furthermore, the findings showed that working conditions has positive impact on employees' performance of tertiary institutions.

Recommendations

It is, therefore, recommended that the role of non-academic staff of tertiary institutions must be cleared to them, content must be explicit to guide against stress and conflict in the workplace. Institutions should also implement policies aimed at controlling and minimizing the level of stress that employees experience.

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